

WORKING WITH TEXTS**Orifjonova Hidoyatkhon Foziljon kizi**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17810318>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 27th November 2025Accepted: 28th November 2025Online: 29th November 2025**KEYWORDS***text, integration, working with text, independent thinking, analysis, synthesis, second synthesis***ABSTRACT***This thesis discusses various methods of working with texts, the direct connection of primary school students with the text while analyzing a literary work, differences between the characters of the work, their characteristics and qualities, as well as the integrated education system..*

It is well known that every subject plays an important role in shaping the younger generation into mature and well-rounded individuals, especially in primary grades, which serve as the foundation for their future. The strength of this foundation directly depends on the subjects taught.

At present, the main objectives of the primary education system are to bring up students as well-rounded individuals, ensure that they acquire deep knowledge, become self-aware, develop logical and critical thinking, and internalize national and universal values. Indeed, primary school knowledge and short literary works play a significant role in developing young readers' interest and love for books.

“Our children must be introduced to small books starting from kindergarten and primary school, and we must nurture them to become genuine book lovers. Only then will a culture of reading develop in our society, and others will also return to reading,” — emphasizes our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.[1]

To begin with, the term text is defined in the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language” as “a written or printed form of an author's work or document” [2]. In Russian and English literature, the word text, derived from the Latin textum, is used to signify “connection,” “interweaving,” or “structure” [3].

Reading is the ability to perceive and practically use written forms of language valued by society and individuals.

From the point of view of volume, texts are divided into two major groups:

1. Small text (microtext)**2. Large text (macrotext)**

Small texts express a single complete idea within their structure. These are short informative texts presenting a brief message — e.g., commercial announcements, newspaper ads, and certain concise official documents [4].

Working with a text involves dividing it into several parts and stages and studying it by analyzing every detail.

The essence of working with texts is to understand the content of the work, explore its ideological and artistic features, and, on this basis, cultivate students' independent thinking skills while providing moral and ethical education. Primary school students are not capable of thoroughly analyzing novels, epics, and long stories, but through reading and analyzing shorter texts, their independent and critical thinking skills begin to develop [4].

When working with texts, special attention must be paid to increasing students' interest. For this purpose, various innovative-integrative methods and games are recommended. During the process of working with a text, students are expected to develop two types of competencies: literary-linguistic competence and literary-analytical competence.

Reading literacy lessons, when conducted in accordance with the requirements of the National Curriculum and connected to real-life experiences and observations, become more effective and help students comprehend texts consciously. These lessons clearly outline educational and developmental goals, reading content by grade levels, methods for developing oral and written speech, and the connection between reading activities and written language.

Literary-linguistic competencies such as listening comprehension, oral and written expression, and reading are developed. Students learn to read fairy tales, legends, stories, and fables clearly and fluently, understand the meanings of words and sentences, express opinions in monologic and dialogic forms, and identify the title, author, and characters of a work. They also learn to express attitudes toward characters and events.

When working with texts, it is effective to use integrated teaching to explore characters' roles, their portraits, and their distinctive traits. Conducting integrated lessons helps primary students build proper concepts about nature and society.

In fact, "the central issue of literary analysis is the analysis conducted through working with the text. While reading, a student becomes familiar with the content of the work, but during analysis, they turn to its poetics. Reading enriches the emotions and sharpens the mind, while analysis helps to study the deeper meaning hidden beneath the text" [5].

Didactic analysis of a literary work consists of three main stages:

First stage — synthesis: students perceive the text as a whole, becoming familiar with its content and expressive elements.

Second stage — analysis: the sequence of events is clarified, and the characters' behavior and nature are identified.

To ensure clear and engaging comprehension of the text, we use plot-based role-playing games. Through such educational games, students learn the text fully and in simple language, forming a complete understanding of it.

Third stage — second synthesis: characters are compared and general conclusions are drawn.

In the second stage, students gather information and clearly identify the characters, and based on this, the third stage — visual and complete performance of roles — is carried out.

This method helps students easily remember and understand the content because they are directly involved in the learning process.

If the text is analyzed purposefully, students learn the topic clearly, simply, interestingly, and consistently. Their attitudes toward their abilities develop, and they understand that all achievements come through effort..

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